

Deliverable D4.4

DiscardLess

Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries

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The Managers story – incentives for discard mitigation and Landing Obligation compliance

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Executive Summary

The overall rationale behind this deliverable is to clarify the views of managers in the DiscardLess case studies on which management measures or tools they favour with regards to implementation of the Landing Obligation and discard reduction. This is important as the views of other stakeholders such as industry and NGOs are readily available in published position statements while the views of managers can only really be obtained by interview and an analysis of actual management actions.

These tools can be seen as one of a suite of approaches which can be taken, along with technical or gear-based and tactical or individual behavioural approaches but in this case they may be employed by managers either at the European, regional, national or industry organisational level.

Box 1: Report highlights

- There is significant diversity in the general approach to LO implementation favoured by managers across the DiscardLess case studies.
- Some favour an emphasis on remote electronic monitoring while others are taking a longer-term approach to incentivising a mindset change throughout the catching sector of the industry.
- Regardless of the overall approach favoured significant inertia is evident in terms of concrete management measures actually applied.
- This may be related to the relatively short time scales within which it is reasonable to expect significant change in such an important policy aspect of fisheries governance.
- The observed inertia may also be related to the fact that some member states may not be as supportive of the need for a change in the approach to discard management as others or at least that some are stronger advocates of the LO as a good vehicle with which to change discard practices.
- High survival and *de minimis* exemptions are the most commonly applied measures but even these can not be considered as being fully applied in the majority of cases as they are not being used by fishers.
- The analysis in this report highlights a very slow progression from identifying the problems to contemplating the solutions but with little real implementation of such solutions as yet.

Box 2: The approaches followed

- Relevant Literature relating to the use of management measures to implement discard policies was reviewed.
- Member State reports on LO implementation were analysed to ascertain which management measures were being used.
- Meetings and workshops with specific relevance to management level input to LO implementation between 2015 and 2018 were attended by DiscardLess partners or published reports from such meetings were analysed.
- A table of available management measures was developed as a tool to discuss managers views on which were most or least useful in LO implementation.
- Interviews were conducted with managers and others with specific management level input across the DiscardLess case studies.

Box 3: How can these results be used and by whom?

- The report compiles information not previously available in a single document on managers views on LO implementation and as such can be used by managers themselves to examine what is being considered or applied in other regional seas.
- Other stakeholders including industry groups and environmental NGO's will also be interested in a summary of the current status of applied management measures and LO implementation.
- The table summarising all management level options or measures will also be useful to stakeholders or managers looking for an alternative or additional approach to those already specified in the Landing Obligation.

Box 4: Policy Recommendations

- A policy catalyst to mobilise management action is required.
- This could take the form of a top-down process whereby failure to implement at least some of the measures available in Article 15 would preclude MS from being able to apply for the use of other more innovative measures such as the removal of choke problem stocks from the TAC system.
- Greater use of positive incentives, such as additional quota in exchange for the use of selective fishing gear, should also help to move implementation forward.
- The necessity for improvement in the monitoring of management measure effectiveness i.e. a reduction in discard rates, is also becoming increasingly evident.

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Glossary

CRP: Cod Recovery Plan

NSAC: North Sea Advisory Council

LO: Landing Obligation

NWWAC: North Western Waters Advisory Council

SWWAC: South Western Waters Advisory Council

MS: Member State

STECF: Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries

CMT: Choke Mitigation Tool

IQF: Inter-species Quota Flexibility

REM: Remote Electronic Monitoring

FDF: Fully Documented Fishery

1 Introduction

The overall rationale behind this task is to clarify the views of managers in the DiscardLess case studies on which management measures or tools they favour with regards to implementation of the Landing Obligation and discard reduction. This is important as the views of other stakeholders such as industry and NGOs are readily available in published position statements while the views of managers can only really be obtained by interview and an analysis of actual management actions.

These tools can be seen as one of a suite of approaches which can be taken, along with technical or gear-based and tactical or individual behavioural approaches but in this case they may be employed by managers either at the European, regional, national or industry organisational level.

Within this overall question we had a particular emphasis on mitigation of choke species situations as chokes have been described as “*the biggest single impediment to implementation of the Landing Obligation*” (North Western Waters Member States Group, 2017). Also it is largely at the management level, as opposed to the operational or individual fisher level, that choke situations can be most effectively addressed.

The NSAC produced a graphic representation of responsibility for preventing chokes in their 2017 advice on implementing the LO (NSAC, 2017) which is reproduced below.

RESPONSIBILITIES PREVENTING CHOKES UNDER THE LANDING OBLIGATION

IN BRUSSELS

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Make legislative proposals to deliver a workable LO

CO-DECISION

Achieve coherence between different EU regulations & achieve overarching CFP objectives

MEMBER STATES

Work in council on delivering CFP objectives

SCIENCE

IN THE CAPITAL

MEMBER STATES

Develop and apply quota flexibilities through national legislation & regional cooperation

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Communicate with regional groups on joint strategies and objectives

PRODUCER ORGANISATIONS

Quota management aimed at minimising choke

NGOS

Work constructively on finding solutions through Advisory Councils

SCIENCE

IN THE HARBOURS

PRODUCER ORGANISATIONS

promoting compliance and voluntary measures

FISHERMEN

At sea application of selectivity & avoidance strategies.

SCIENCE

In this report we are mainly interested in how the actions of managers can stimulate, or not, the development and uptake of measures, such as selectivity improvements in fishing gear for example, rather than how such measures are utilized at the operational level of skippers. So we are examining the views of those operating at all levels in the NSAC hierarchy above with the exception of individual vessels.

Our definition of managers thus encompasses anyone who is responsible for designing or implementing management measures with an emphasis on discards. This includes policy makers at EU level, national level administrators and groups of stakeholders to whom some significant responsibility for quota management has been delegated.

2 Approach taken

In order to compile this report we have attended meetings and workshops where high level discard mitigation and LO implementation strategies have been discussed by managers. We have examined the recent literature on management measures and incentives aimed at mitigation of discards and also EU reports on meetings and discard plans. Following this we collaboratively produced a table of management measures, which had been proposed at various fora and from diverse sources including industry groups, member state high level groups, advisory councils and NGO's.

The table was used as a tool to discuss management measures in interviews with managers across 8 different countries covering 8 DiscardLess case studies. The case studies covered were the North

Sea, West of Scotland, Celtic Sea, Eastern English Channel, Bay of Biscay, West Mediterranean, East Mediterranean and the Azores. Views of managers in each of these case studies are described in detail in Section 6.

Following these interviews and in conjunction with analysis of actual measures taken as documented in Member State reports on LO implementation we have looked at commonalities and differences across regions and case studies and made some conclusions regarding what may be useful measures for the future.

3 Information and Literature sources

Due to the volume of documents from multiple viewpoints generated over the past few years regarding LO implementation we have not tried to analyse everything published. The list below is a summary of what we believe to be the most relevant to the issue of how management measures can contribute to the implementation of the LO:

- Various adopted EU Discard Plans from 2015 to 2018
- Member State Landing Obligation implementation progress reports 2016
- STECF reports: in particular reports on annual evaluations of joint recommendations for discard plans (e.g. STECF-17-08) and STECF 16-13 Methodology and data requirements for reporting on the Landing Obligation
- Proceedings of Brussels Landing Obligation seminars – dates
 - EU Commission Seminar 24th February 2016 (https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/seminar-landing-obligation_en)
 - DG MARE hosted Landing Obligation Seminar, Brussels, November 15th, 2017, (https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/sites/fisheries/files/docs/pages/landing-obligation-seminar-november-2017-summary_en.pdf)
- Proceedings and attendance at various Quota swop workshops including:
 - Copenhagen, 11th March 2016
 - Edinburgh, 14th and 15th April, 2016
- North Sea Advisory Council Choke Avoidance Measures Symposium, Copenhagen, 2-3rd November 2016.
- Joint AC Member States Choke Expert meeting, 19-20th September 2017 Wednesday, 20 September 2017, Venue: BIM, Dun Laoghaire, Ireland.
- EU Discard Reduction Manual, Environmental Defense Fund.
- DiscardLess Case Study annual reports 2016 and 2017.
- Various Advisory Council and Member State Group advice and associated correspondence with the EU Commission including:
 - NSAC Advice Ref. 02-1516 Implementation of the Landing Obligation, 24th February 2016

- NSAC Advice Ref. 14-1617^[11]_[SEP] Managing Fisheries within the Landing Obligation, 4th October 2017
- EU Commission reply of 16th November 2017 to NSAC Advice Ref.14-1617.
- NWW Member State and Advisory Council group NWW Choke Species Analysis report, October 2017.
- Letter of 16th November 2017 from NWW Member State and Advisory Council group to EU Commission on dealing with choke species issues and the letter in reply from the EU Commission of 11th January 2018.
- Meetings and interviews were also held with administration staff responsible for Landing Obligation implementation in 7 different Member States covering 8 case studies. Meetings with industry groups with responsibility for quota management were also held.
- Additionally a Commission staff member working on the Landing Obligation was interviewed.

4 Review of relevant documents and meetings regarding management measures

North Sea Advisory Council

The North Sea Advisory Council established a Landing Obligation Focus Group in January 2015 and since then they have produced and made publically available through their website a number of comprehensive position papers on LO implementation. We have examined two of these in particular detail.

The first document, NSAC Advice Ref. 02-1516 Implementation of the Landing Obligation, was agreed by the NSAC on 24th February 2016. It contains a detailed discussion of the merits of numerous management measures and lists the following mitigation options in order of their priority as seen by the NSAC:

- Avoidance of unwanted catches;
- High survival exemptions;
- Adjustments to TACs and quotas;
- De minimis exemptions;
- Interspecies flexibility;

- Additional technical measures that focus on meeting the requirements of the landing obligation;
- Inter-annual quota flexibilities.

The document recognised that even with application of all available exemptions, flexibilities and measures within Article 15 of the CFP chokes may still occur.

Some additional measures were described in the document, with the proviso that they did not all necessarily have the full support of the NSAC, including:

- The grouping of low volume choke species within an “others” quota.
- Removal of TACs for some stocks for various reasons.
- Reviewing the provisions for a landing obligation as part of the reformed CFP, through reconsideration of the terms of Article 15.
- End of year or retrospective quota adjustments or transfers to avoid fleet tie-ups.
- Financed fleet reduction under EMFF.

The document also contained a preliminary analysis of which specific fisheries may create the most significant choke issues.

The second significant document agreed on 4th October 2017 by the NSAC was titled “*Managing Fisheries within the Landing Obligation*”, NSAC Advice Ref. 14-1617. This second document attempts to “*look beyond Article 15 at additional measures that could bolster those already in the management ‘toolbox’ and be introduced, either immediately or over a longer period to address the challenges of the LO.*” The document refers to measures which have been taken to adapt to the LO and selectivity improvements are specifically mentioned and the document refers to the DiscardLess Selectivity Manual for support on this point. The document also references the NSAC hosted Choke Symposium held in Copenhagen on 2 November 2016 where new potential measures to mitigate choke impacts were discussed.

The following measures are discussed in the paper:

Predictive analysis

- To what extent it is possible to predict when chokes will arise

Avoidance, information sharing and gear selectivity

- Avoidance^{[L]_{SEP}}
- Information sharing
- Real-time closures
- Precautionary areas
- Move-on policy^{[L]_{SEP}}

- Seasonal closures
- Gear selectivity

The application of TACs

- Data Limited Stocks
- Use of FMSY ranges
- Grouping of TACs^[1]_[SEP]
- Removing TACs
- By-catch quota^[1]_[SEP]
- Prohibited species
- Zero TAC species

Quota Management Considerations

- Domestic quota management
- Quota uplifts
- Quota swaps & transfers

The document describes an alternative approach to management based on differentiating between primary or target and secondary or bycatch species and refers to Australia as an example of where such an approach is applied. The conclusion drawn by the NSAC is that for primary species the existing tools available are most likely sufficient to resolve choke problems but for secondary species, which may be data poor species a risk-based bycatch management approach could be applied, as it is in the Australian system, in order to avoid choke problems.

The document also acknowledges that *“the successful implementation of the LO will be heavily dependent on the degree to which the fishing industry takes ownership of the issue”*.

NWW process including move to use of Choke Mitigation Tool (CMT).

The High-Level Group NWWHLG and the Advisory Council NWWAC jointly conducted a Choke analysis using an analytical tool, the choke mitigation tool, to assess which stocks created the greatest risk of choke situations arising, to categorise those into high, medium and low risk categories and to evaluate which mitigation measures were most likely to be effective in dealing with chokes. A report on this process was published in October 2017 with stated aim *“to use this analysis to identify residual choke issues that can only be addressed at Union level with alternative measures over and above the existing tools available”*. Subsequently on November 16th 2017 a letter from the joint group was sent to the European Commission, which stressed that with the application of all available measures some residual choke problems would remain. The letter goes on to say that *“The Group is strongly committed to keep on working on the pursuit of solutions within the current framework, but in case this scope was not sufficient, we will require a closer cooperation with the European Commission to consider alternative measures outside the existing toolbox”*. The phrase *“a change in management approach may be required”* is used several times in the letter without specifying exactly what that change might be. This contrasts with the more explicit NSAC

advice which raises the Australian system of differentiating between primary and secondary species.

EC responses

So in late 2017 there has been a progressive move towards a position where the ACs and MS groups are looking for guidance from the Commission on more radical solutions to choke problems, or *“specific suggestions (beyond those already outlined in the choke toolbox) on how we might jointly tackle the serious impediments to a fully implemented and effective LO”*.

The Commission replies to both parties and their responses are interesting in illustrating the state of play in terms of management measures and LO implementation.

Firstly in their response to the NSAC on November 16th 2017 the Commission addresses the NSAC question regarding the differentiation between primary (or targeted) stocks and secondary (or by-catch) stocks and says *“As you know, the European Parliament and Council are currently negotiating the North Sea Demersal Multi-annual Plan which sets out the management targets for different groups of stocks in the North Sea. The Commission fully relies on the ability of the co-legislators to agree on an outcome which is in line with the CFP Basic Regulation, allows managing all fish stocks in a sustainable manner and helps to alleviate potential choke issues.”*

The letter goes on to state *“Finally, I've read with interest your very concrete suggestion regarding the replacement of the TACs for deep-sea and semi deep-sea species by bycatch limits. We will examine this potential measure and discuss it with Member States and stakeholders early in 2018 with a view of the fishing opportunities regulation 2019.”*

In response to the NWWHLG and NWWAC letter the response seems far less equivocal. The letter states clearly that there is more work to be done using existing measures *“We believe there is still a margin of progress in identifying solutions based on the tools available in the toolbox”* and it specifically mentions reviewing national quota allocation regimes and further selectivity improvements as examples.

The Commission response then states *“Let me at this point also mention that we are concerned about control and the documentation of catches”* and it then refers to a *“lack of compliance”* indicated by all analyses of the LO implementation to date. Only at the end does the letter mention additional measures: *“Finally, where there is evidence that choke situations would still remain even when all the available tools have been exhausted, we will reflect on what additional measures may be required”*.

So it appears that the most recent illustration of how the Commission is thinking on management measures is that all currently available measures, including control and monitoring must be fully implemented before novel solutions can be utilised.

Other workshops and seminars.

A number of dedicated fora, workshops and seminars were held in 2016 and 2017 and which were focussed on a detailed discussion of how significant choke problems could be resolved.

- Copenhagen, 11th March 2016
- Edinburgh, 14th and 15th April, 2016
- North Sea Advisory Council Choke Avoidance Measures Symposium, Copenhagen, 2-3rd November 2016.
- Joint AC- MEMBER STATES Choke Expert meeting, 19-20 September 2017 Dublin, Ireland.
- EU Commission Seminar, Brussels, 24th February 2016
- DG MARE Seminar on the Landing Obligation, Brussels, 15th November, 2017.

5 Table of management measures

In order to focus our discussions with managers on their preferences regarding which management measures were most (or least) useful in terms of LO implementation and choke mitigation we developed a table of management measures (Table 1 below). The measures included in the table were drawn from diverse sources including industry proposals, advisory council position statements, NGO publications and measures used in non-EU fisheries management regimes, e.g. USA, New Zealand.

The measures were categorised into groupings such as technical measures, quota based measures, economic measures etc.

It was not intended to discuss all of the measures in the table with managers in each case study but to use it as a starting point for a discussion on preferences. We also felt that inclusion of some measures such as RTI's, the Deemed Value system from New Zealand or the Risk Pool approach from the US which may be less widely known or discussed could serve to stimulate a more open discussion which could potentially move beyond the "usual suspects" in the discard mitigation debate such as selectivity improvements.

Our table is not the same as the CMT mitigation actions because they cover actions at all stakeholder levels whereas in this case we are considering only actions for which management can play a significant role.

Discuss categories of management options and describe how the measure works. e.g. Inter species flexibility – occurs at MS level - Up to 9% of the target species quota provided the non-target species is within safe biological limits (CFP Article 15(8))

Management measures incorporated in the list were drawn from a number of sources including:

- North Sea Advisory Council toolbox of choke mitigation measures,
- EDF discard reduction manual
- Workshops on choke species held in 2016,
- Measures suggested at DiscardLess, Advisory Council and EU level meetings,
- Generic lists of management measures e.g. FAO 2009 A Fishery Managers Guidebook.

Table 1: DiscardLess Task 4.4 Measures potentially available to managers for discard mitigation and Landing Obligation compliance.

Category	Measure	Examples/Specific cases	Pros	Cons	Managers Role	Comments
Technical Measures	Selectivity Improvements	Mesh size increase, SMPs, Grids	e.g. industry support and interest	e.g. potential economic losses to industry	e.g. Incentivising through quota allocation.	
	MCRS, maximum sizes	Changes in MCRS e.g. Nephrops in Skaggerak				
	Spatial management	Temporary Spawning Area Closures, Real time closures.				
	Temporal measures	Temporary/seasonal cessation of fishing				
Tactical	Avoidance	Avoidance of high discard areas – can be at individual, group (through industry info sharing) or national level through official spatial closures or move-on rules.				
	Avoidance	Fishing at different depths or by switching gear				
Quota based	Quota uplift	Based on historic discard rates Use to adjust Relative Stability				
	Interspecies flexibility	Up to 9% of the target species quota provided the non-target species is within safe biological limits (CFP Article 15(8))				
	Setting of TACs and quotas for relevant species	MSY flexibility - For mixed fisheries set TACs slightly below Fmsy for target species and slightly above Fmsy for choke species in order to balance out risk				

	Transnational Quota swaps	Obligatory swapping of under-used quotas				
	Transnational Quota swaps	Regional transnational pool of TAC/quota to alleviate chokes				
	MS internal quota allocation & management	Sweden – annual quotas Ireland – vessel specific monthly quotas				
	10% Inter-annual flexibility – banking and borrowing	10% carryover between years. As per CFP Article 15(9)				
	In-year quota flexibility	Payback or carry over of quota between allocation periods				
	Individual Quotas	Denmark				
	Co-op/PO/Collective quota management	France/UK				
	Risk pooling	US west coast low TAC rockfish species				
	Removal/suspension of TAC	Proposal from Advisory Councils for cases where there is risk of extreme economic impacts from small TAC species e.g. Whiting in Irish Sea Nephrops fishery				
	Deemed Values	New Zealand bycatch rules				
Input controls	Individual Quotas	Denmark				
	Limited Licences/Access restrictions	Most EU pelagic fisheries				
	Decommissioning					
	Effort based controls	Days at Sea Individual Transferable Effort				
Exemptions	<i>De minimis</i>	CFP Article 15 (4c)				
	High Survival	CFP Article 15 (4b)				

Control Based approaches	Fully documented fishery	Denmark, UK Nephrops vessels				
	Enhanced observer coverage	US west coast groundfish fisheries – up to 200% observer coverage (Alaska Pollock)				
Innovative or non-categorical approaches	Real Time Incentives	Theory				
	Voluntary industry implemented daily quotas	Balearic daily Dolphin fish quota				

Explanatory notes:

Risk pooling – US West Coast low TAC rockfish species – managers in this case attempt to limit the potential negative economic impact of low TAC non-target species by requiring groups of fishers to pool their quota for bycatch species. Member of the group pay either money or quota in order to have access to the quota pool. There are usually additional avoidance measures such as gear switching and area closures which group members are required to adhere to.

Deemed Value – a system used in New Zealand which requires fishermen to pay a pre-agreed fee for landing bycatch species for which they do not have quota. Theoretically the fee should be set high enough to act as a deterrent to excessive catches but low enough to avoid the creation of widespread non-compliance and misreporting.

Real Time Incentives (RTI) - a fisheries-management approach based on a single allowance of fishing-impact credits. According to this concept, fishing mortality rates of multiple species and ecosystem impacts are regulated through a single currency. Fishers can fish where and when they want and spend their allocated RTIs according to spatiotemporally varying tariffs set by managers. The RTI spending rate is determined by the time spent in areas with different tariffs.

6 Managers views from the case studies

In this section for each of the DiscardLess case studies we report on interviews or meetings with managers and also the 2016 LO implementation reports submitted by the relevant Member State. This gives us an indication of what has actually happened with regards to management measures in the case study and also what the future plans or intentions of the managers are.

Regarding the interviews with managers in each case we attempt to at least address the following questions:

- Which measures did managers express a preference for and why?
- Which measures specifically do managers view as being useful in mitigating choke situations?
- Did managers express a dislike for any particular measures and why?
- Is there an appetite for LO implementation or is it seen as an external imposition?

6.1 Celtic Sea Case Study: Ireland

Summary of management measures references in the Irish response to the Commissions 2016 request for information on LO implementation.

- The report describes vessel trials (some conducted as Challenge Trials through the DiscardLess project) which tested the efficacy of gear changes and spatial avoidance tactics aimed at discard reduction.
- Details trials aimed at reducing catches of below MCRS Nephrops.
- Describes a new regulation that requires an increase in minimum codend mesh size from 70 to 80 mm for all Irish vessels over 12m that deploy more than one demersal trawl from January 2017.
- Describes successful trial of T90 codend selectivity improvements for Whiting – this is currently a voluntary measure.
- A successful trial of separator panels to separate fish and Nephrops is described but it is noted that current regulations prohibit the use of such gears and regional agreement between MS would be required in order for such gear to be used.
- Fishery Improvement Projects were planned in 2017 to improve uptake of these measures
- LO related changes to quota management regime. “A number of changes have been made to the Irish quota management system with significant amendments to the Monkfish notifications & fishery management notifications as well as the monthly whitefish data. In addition to this a significant IT project has been initiated to look at a new quota management system capable of

dealing with quota management once the landing obligation is fully phased in. An additional catch-limit is made available each month for obligated vessels for obligated species over and above the catch limits in place to mitigate the potential choke effect”.

- Analysis process of choke problems is described which was conducted in collaboration with the NWWAC. The report mentions possible measures to mitigate chokes including improved selectivity, *de minimis* and high survivability exemptions, inter species quota flexibility.
- 3 *de minimis* exemptions relevant to Ireland were established (for whiting caught with bottom trawls and seines ≥ 100 mm in ICES divisions VIIb-VIIj, for whiting caught with bottom trawls and seines < 100 mm in ICES subarea VII (excluding VIIa, VIId and VIIe) and for Nephrops in ICES subarea VII).
- 1 high survival exemption relevant to Ireland was established (Norway lobster caught by pots, traps or creels in ICES division VI and subarea VII)
- The total *de minimis* related discards of Nephrops and Whiting logged by Irish vessels in 2016 amounted to 45 tonnes
- Inter annual or inter specific flexibility provisions were not used.
- LO related communication initiatives with industry from both the fisheries department and control authorities were described.
- Funding has been provided for 9 projects to invest in more selective gears with a relevance to the LO.
- 2 projects to improve port infrastructure to handle unwanted catches were assessed in 2016 with an estimated funding of €500k.
- Some difficulties with LO implementation were noted including demersal bycatch in pelagic fisheries, lack of funding to adapt fishing gears, vessels or port infrastructure, difficulties implementing and monitoring *de minimis* or high survivability exemptions, increased incidence of refusal to carry observers.

Summary of meeting with Fisheries Department (DAFM) staff responsible for administration of LO, November 2017.

A change to the pelagic quota management regime, labelled the Pilot Quota Balancing scheme, was discussed. This scheme creates a mechanism whereby catches of species for which a vessel did not have an allocation or catches over the vessels allocated quota could be repaid in a subsequent fishing period. The scheme in part was intended to deal with opportunistic behaviour whereby some fishers were landing accidental catches of pelagic fish as obligated under the LO. The possibility of the scheme being used in order to provide some flexibility to deal with chokes in the context of a non-tradeable quota regime was uncertain and DAFM staff emphasised that it was a learning process. It is intended that the scheme although initially only applying to the pelagic fishery would be expanded to include demersal fisheries also.

The general thrust of the Quota Balancing system is that fishers will pay for overshooting their quota with the repayment (in the next fishing period whatever that might be) being ramped up depending on the degree of overfishing. Currently the repayment/overfishing set up is:

Up to 10% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.0

Over 10% up to 20% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.2

Over 20% up to 40% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.4

Over 40% up to 50% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 1.8

Any further overfishing greater than 50% of allocation - Overfishing repayment 2.0.

Although the quota balancing scheme is intended to be in place for the start of 2018 some uncertainty existed regarding how the overfishing events that the scheme is designed to address would be dealt with by the fisheries control agency.

It was also emphasised that the scheme was only a partial solution to LO issues and that further (unspecified) measures will most likely follow in 2018.

In relation to other management measures DAFM staff were of the opinion that international swaps had not been affected by the LO, or at least not yet. In fact all of the traditional swaps utilized by Ireland had continued in the past few years and a few new ones (e.g. Boarfish) had taken place also.

Haddock in the Celtic Sea was mentioned as a case study where significant choke problems would occur. DAFM opinion was that a combination of available measures would help to mitigate but would most likely not entirely solve the problem. Measures mentioned which would collectively contribute were:

- International swaps (but limited by the fact that quota for this stock is limited for all countries)
- Quota top-up
- Inter species flexibility
- End of year quota banking and borrowing mechanism
- Use of TAC ranges
- Technical measures – in particular larger mesh sizes which are already being examined for a number of species.
- Bycatch limits in place of target species quotas – an example was given of Rockall Haddock for vessels targeting Megrin. (details of scheme in Annex 1) Bluefin tuna was also given as an example of a bycatch quota.
- The use of more focused subgroups within the general monthly quota regime – e.g. the existing Monkfish scheme whereby vessels who wished to receive additional allocation of Monkfish quota had to forfeit quota for certain other species and also commit to an annual tie-up period.

The following example, from the November 2017 Irish Fisheries Management Notices (DAFM, 2017), shows how the Rockall Haddock bycatch allowance is managed. In the month of November, an Irish sea-fishing boat greater than or equal to 55 feet in length, must stop targetting Haddock in Area VI & Vb when 10 tonnes of Haddock has been landed or retained on board. Subsequently the boat may only

target Non-Gadoid species in Area VI, Vb. The vessel then has a 400kg bycatch allowance and when that is caught the boat may not fish in Area VI, Vb for the remainder of the month.

A pilot scheme introduced in 2017 to promote the use of selective gears in the Nephrops fishery was also discussed (see Annex 1 for details). Unfortunately the scheme was only introduced very late in the year so only 1 vessel applied but it is intended that the scheme will be reintroduced in 2018. A similar approach may also be applied with vessels targeting Whiting in 2018.

A difficulty mentioned with all of these management adaptations is that there is a lot of work involved in setting them up and managing them and personnel numbers are limited.

The possibility of withdrawing a stock from the TAC process was discussed and DAFM staff felt that before that could happen it would have to be demonstrated that everything else possible has been tried. In the case of Irish Sea Whiting which was an example of a stock where derogation from TAC was proposed a lot of selectivity trials have been done already including with a SELTRA trawl.

Area closures would only be possible on an industry voluntary basis. This may work but it would not be possible for DAFM to administer a real time system.

DAFM staff mentioned that bycatch allowances and LO measures in general were difficult to enforce but that such bycatch schemes promote avoidance at least.

They also felt that eventually market pressures will push the responsibility for compliance on to fishers. They mentioned changes in the buying practices of large French and Spanish supermarket chains and major seafood companies in terms of responsibility.

There was no appetite for ITQs as DAFM staff felt that ITQs in other countries had high social costs in terms of reduced numbers of smaller vessels and an adverse impact on smaller ports.

Onboard cameras were not greatly supported as there was a feeling that it takes more than the allocation of some extra quota to change underlying fishing practices. Camera usage could be appropriate on large pelagic vessels but not on smaller vessels.

Alterations to relative stability keys in the case of quota uplift were not seen as a realistic possibility.

6.2 French case studies.

The French administration and fisheries industry created in 2014 a specific working group “MOOD” to discuss LO related implementation issues and impacts in France. This working Group was composed of members of the National fisheries administration (DPMA), scientists, PO's and Regional Fisheries Committees. During MOOD meetings members jointly discussed the positioning of France during intergovernmental meetings for the preparation of discard plans in regional Seas where French fleets are operating. The results of each intergovernmental meeting were also presented and discussed within the WG. From physical meeting organized in Paris the WG currently holds virtual meetings every month.

It is within this group that LO exemptions requested by France were discussed with the agreement of all participants. Additionally this WG sees one of its responsibilities as the increased awareness of the LO and its impact on the French fleet, harbours and territories. Fisheries industry representatives and in particular PO's understand that adaptation to the LO requires an improvement of fishing gear selectivity. Since the first meetings of the WG until today many fishing gear selectivity projects were undertaken by PO's or other industry organisations and scientists with the objective to improve selectivity and limit discards in almost all regional seas (North Sea and East English Channel, West English Channel, Celtic Sea, Bay of Biscay, Mediterranean). The majority of these projects were financed by France Filière Pêche, a joint organization representing all sectors of the French Fishing Industry from production to marketing.

Once the exemptions requested by France were granted other projects have been financed. This time the objective was to obtain data about the survival of some species (eg. nephrops or sole) and increase the rate of survival. For example to increase the survival rate of nephrops a new sorting table was introduced. So, crew members could put the undersize nephrops directly into water to wait until the end of sorting out process. This new sorting table was easily accepted by the crew members because it improved their working conditions as they are standing up to sort fish instead of sitting down.

In total the number of these projects is around 12 with the first starting in 2011 and ending in 2016. These projects have shown the impacts of the use of more selective gears on discard reduction and also the losses of commercial species. Some of the trials were positive regarding discard reduction and also have been supported by fishers. An example is the case of the use of bigger mesh for trawlers operating in the Western Channel which has decreased considerably their catches of choke species, in particular boarfish, for which France does not have quota while at the same time not losing too many commercially valuable fish.

In the Eastern Channel the EODE project and other studies have shown that given the species targeted at some periods of the year (red mullet, squids) it was difficult to reduce unwanted catches without significant commercial losses. In these cases there is not much uptake of these selectivity devices. The EODE project has also shown that sorting time will increase a lot in a LO context. So while improvements in fishing gear selectivity appears to be the preferred option of the French industry it will require more time first to find the right gear for particular species or areas and also to convince French boat owners and crew about the efficiency of the new gears.

Despite this positive work undertaken by the French industry the French Fisheries Administration didn't mention it in the note addressed to DG MARE in February 2017. This note gave an overview of the general situation without detailing the effort undertaken by the industry on selectivity but this may be a result of the specific questions asked by DG MARE. The note mentions the difficulties encountered by vessel owners in recording discards in the logbook and distinguishing which category they belong in (predator damage, resulting from contamination, or if they are undersize, etc). The note also mentions efforts taken by the administration in terms of communication about the LO and its implementation towards fisher's representatives or directly to vessels owners through the production of informative notes found on the website of DPMA and the exemptions granted in national law through the publication of bylaws.

In addition to this general vision we have conducted meetings and interviews within Discardless with PO's, Fisheries Committees, large fishing companies and Administration managers.

For the French administration the French fleet does not face a particular problem relating to LO implementation because quotas for the main commercial species are high enough. In the case of a choke species problem, e.g. with boarfish in the Western Channel, for which France doesn't have any quotas, it is possible to exchange with one of the countries having quotas.

Regarding the issue of reporting discards in the logbook for the moment not many vessels have done it. The incentive of a quota uplift was not enough to encourage fishers to register discards. It seems that one PO registered discards and asked to uplift quotas in West English Channel. According to another PO, the other reason that boat owners and skippers don't report discards is because first they don't understand why they should do it and second technical difficulties don't make it easy for them. They should declare the weight on a species-specific basis and not the total amount of discards. All managers agree that recording of discards is necessary to justify the *de minimis* exemptions granted. Otherwise nobody could understand why we claim such exemptions if our recorded discards don't show it. For all of them if discards are not recorded yet is because the rule is not yet controlled as the emphasis during this transition period is on communication about the LO rather than implementation.

Some PO's consider that it is important to quantify precisely all the catches and to record total catches including discards, but fishers "*are afraid about the impact of such records*".

Quota uplifts are seen as a solution to discard problems by some but there remains an issue regarding understanding that the uplift quota is not the commercial quota.

Choke species are perceived as the main problem especially for species with restrictive quotas. These species should be classified in the same category as protected species (e.g. Undulate ray), which are forbidden to be landed.

Swaps are seen as a partial solution to restrictive quota or zero quota species but "*finding an interesting exchange*" is the key particularly for species with little community quota.

PO representatives from Boulogne sur Mer mentioned quota adaptation as a useful measure. They said that as no selective/tactical adaptation were really envisaged by fishermen they really focused on quota optimization (trade with other national/European POs). Of course it was something that was already done in the past but they really try to see what could be the potential problematic species and try to anticipate future quota trades (increase the existing links) to avoid running out of quotas.

Regarding *de minimis* exemptions some seek flexibility by combining species. If exempted species were combined e.g. monkfish, skipjack and rays, then the calculation of percentages is bigger than only one as it is now. In Brittany there is room for maneuver on species such as monkfish but this is not necessarily the case for other French regions. For such regions the establishment of a combined or global *de minimis* is a possible solution.

All parties consider that the implementation of article 15 is difficult which leads them to delay the process of implementation.

6.3 Mediterranean Case Study

To know the views of managers from the Mediterranean Case Studies, different meetings have been held with the main local stakeholders between 2015 and the present (Feb-2018) (Table 1; see also Deliverable D8.7): Directorate of Fisheries from the Catalan Government; Directorate of Fisheries from the Balearic Islands Government; Fisheries Association of Catalonia; Fisheries Association of the Balearic Islands. A meeting was also held with the MEDAC and the NGO Oceana. Hereafter, the term stakeholders is used to refer to all these interviewed actors: managers (local and national), representatives of the fishing sector (local and regional) and the NGO Oceana.

Table 1. Meetings carried out during the DiscardLess project with stakeholders from the Western and Eastern Mediterranean. Acronyms are: Directorate of Fisheries from the Catalan Government (GDF-CAT); Directorate of Fisheries from the Balearic Islands Government (GDF-BI); Fisheries Association of Catalonia (FA-CAT); Fisheries Association of the Balearic Islands (FA-BI).

Case Study	Date	City	Attendants	Country
Western Med	22/04/2015	Bilbao, kick-off meeting	GDF-CAT; GDF-BI; POs AMOP; POs CRPMEM	France, Spain
	8/04/2016	Sète	POs SATHOAN; POs du Sud	France
	14/06/2016	Barcelona	GDF-CAT	Spain
	11/07/2016	Palma de Mallorca	GDF-IB; FA-BI; FA-CAT	Spain
	3/11/2016	Madrid	Spanish Ministry of Fisheries	Spain
	29/11/2016	Rome	MEDAC	Spain
	30/01/2017	Madrid (Skype)	Oceana	Spain
	25/11/2017	Palma de Mallorca	GDF-IB; FA-BI	Spain
	11/01/2018	Palma de Mallorca	GDF-IB; FA-BI	Spain

At any level (regional, national and local), all Med stakeholders interviewed agreed on the necessity of reducing discards, which are seen as a food waste of catches and a negative impact on marine ecosystems. In spite of this, all stakeholders also agreed both on their full opposition to the Landing Obligation (LO) as it stands and on the measures that should be undertaken to reduce discards in the Med. Stakeholders consider the LO a wrong regulation that no one believes in, neither the fishing industry nor the administration. Most stakeholders think that instead of developing a new fishing regulation such as the LO, it would have been better to improve the enforcement of the existing ones to reduce fishing impacts on stocks and ecosystems. This disagreement, however, does not preclude that once the LO was enacted, all stakeholders are doing their best for its implementation.

For stakeholders, the LO is seen as tailored for Atlantic fisheries under TACs regulation, but not applicable to the Med, where species are regulated by technical measures such as fishing effort and gear control. According to Article 15 of the Common Fisheries Policy (Regulation EU N° 1380/2013), the LO in the Med applies to catches of species which are subjected to minimum sizes (a total of 27 taxa²) as defined in Annex III of Regulation (EC) N° 1967/2006. The reasons whereby the implementation of the LO would not be feasible in the Med are varied, but the most limiting factor is the lack of fish processing industries or, when available, the long distances to the fishing ports that would increase excessively the transportation costs. The large number of ports along the continental coast and the existence of numerous islands (e.g. Greece) compound the transportation problem.

Furthermore, owing to the Med fleet characteristics (most vessels are less than 10 m long and the small-scale fishery represents the 80% in number of vessels) the volumes of discards by boat are too small to sustain specific discard treatment industries. According to stakeholders, the fleet characteristics also represent a constraint when processing discards on board. The storing capacity of the vessels is very limited and in some cases the burden may be risky for security sailing. Sanitary regulations that do not allow mixing the discarded fraction with the commercial catch may also be a problem. Fishery representatives sustain that, if needed, the sector cannot assume investments to tackle the implementation of the LO; most Med vessels are family, small-sized enterprises.

For Med stakeholders the LO goes against the efforts made during the last decades to reduce the commercialization of small-sized fish. Both managers and fishers have to change their minds because the previous prohibition of carrying small-sized fish, both at sea and on the road, is now abolished under the LO. Stakeholders also hold that this new scenario will allow increasing the black market of illegal fish. According to managers, this demands substantial improvements in the control system. Disagreements between administrations (i.e. national and regional) should be avoided and the surveillance has to be improved substantially to enable tracking the discards fate.

For Oceana, the main concern of the LO is the lack of measures to discourage the harvest of unwanted catches at sea. This is particularly urgent in the Med where the incentives mechanisms to avoid unwanted catches present in the Atlantic are missing. To avoid the black market of undersized fish due to the lack of those incentives, the NGO proposes that discouraging mechanisms should be defined in the Med. For instance, by means of fuel price reductions or giving priority to specific fishing grounds to fishers using more selective and less impacting gears. Furthermore, the incomes obtained from the

² Including species, genera (e.g. *Mullus* spp.) and a whole family (Palinuridae).

selling of discards should not be for individual fishermen but shared for community purposes (e.g. research, social funds).

Once listed the main concerns of stakeholders to the current LO, they also agree on the alternatives to adopt in order to reduce discards in the Med. First of all, they consider that the LO should be generalized to include as many species as possible to reduce wasting catches and impacts on the ecosystems rather than focusing it exclusively on those taxa having MLS.

All stakeholders hold that the measures that should be implemented to reduce discards in the Med are: i) improvement of selectivity; and 2) use of spatio-temporal closures for effort control³. The change in mesh geometry (40 mm diamond to square mesh in the cod-end) was an important step (Council Regulation (EC) 1967/2006), but its use is not general in the Med owing to the exemption that permits using the 50 mm diamond mesh (under the condition of demonstrating equivalent or higher selectivity than that of the 40 mm square mesh). According to stakeholders, efforts should be done to generalize the use of the 40 mm square mesh. Improvements on gear selectivity should keep on, not only to reduce discards but also to improve the fishing exploitation scheme (e.g. reductions of direct impact on the seabed and fuel consumption).

However, some French fishery representatives inform that this measure is very unpopular among the sector because further improvements in selectivity would not be possible. Owing to the high multispecificity of the bottom trawl fishery, which takes a large number of species with different forms and sizes, it will necessarily lead to significant commercial losses. For this reason, they defend the use of spatio-temporal selectivity measures to the point that a local fishermen organization has funded a scientific project in that direction (GALION project).

Stakeholders sustain that spatio-temporal closures should be applied using scientific criteria. To protect recruitment, both the fishermen skill and the available scientific knowledge will allow identifying the best seasons, depths and/or areas to be closed for fisheries management (Colloca *et al*, 2015). However, in some places this can be a problem since it is difficult to find alternative fishing areas. In this sense, Med representatives of the fishing sector think that incorporating stakeholders in research projects such as DiscardLess is a welcomed, successful initiative.

³ These measures agree with recent scientific reports (Colloca *et al*. 2013. Rebuilding Mediterranean fisheries: a new paradigm for ecological sustainability. *Fish and Fisheries*, 14: 89-109; Vasilakopoulos *et al*. 2014. The alarming decline of Mediterranean fish stocks. *Current Biology*, 24(14): 1643-1648).

According to the stakeholders, the LO should be applied locally in order to be successful, through co-management. The number of co-management initiatives in the Med is numerous. Here we report a recent one arisen from a technical seminar organized by DiscardLess, together with the General Directorate of Fisheries (GDF-BI) and the Fishermen Association of the Balearic Islands (FA-BI), on November 2017. The main objective was to inform the fishing sector about different technical measures and strategies that could be used to reduce the impact of this fishery, including discards. The most interesting measure for fishers was the introduction of mid-water doors, probably because it reduced, not only the direct impact on the seabed, but also the fuel consumption with the consequent reduction of operating costs. In fact, on 30 December 2017 the GDF-BI published a call for grants to the fishing sector to develop the measure 1.1.2 included in the Spanish operational program of the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF): "Limitation of the impact of fishing on the marine environment and adaptation of fisheries to the protection of species. Change of doors". Currently (Feb-2018), managers (GD-BI), fishers (FA-BI) and scientists (IEO) are establishing agreements for the development of experimental fishing pilot projects to assess this initiative and new measures for the improvement of the ecological and economic efficiency of the commercial fisheries from the Balearic Islands.

For the MEDAC, Med fishers should no longer see EU regulations as tailored only to Atlantic fisheries, they must change their minds. In this respect, and contrary to some years ago, this Advisory Council holds that Med fishers begin to think that improving the gear selectivity and other initiatives within the Marine Strategy Framework, such as evaluating additional sources of impact on the marine environment, proposing closure periods and creating fishery restricted areas, would be beneficial.

6.4 Bay of Biscay case study: Spain

Spain has been quite proactive and strategic in organising internal meetings with the aim of implementing the LO and has focused the main implementation actions through the “Mesa Estatal para la Eliminación de los Descartes”. This group has been structured through a set of meetings and workshops, in which managers, sector and scientific institutions have discussed ways of approaching the landing obligation in a coordinated manner.

The group started by defining the priority areas where fisheries technical measures could have a real option of improving selectivity. Furthermore, the main fishery selected was the trawlers operating in the Bay of Biscay and Iberian Atlantic waters (the case study selected for DiscardLess). In this fishery several technical options (mainly escape grids under different configurations) have been tested. Results are promising, although still there is some reluctance by the sector to apply them, given the economic impact of loss of retention of other commercial species which has been demonstrated in AZTI surveys (Prellezo *et al*, 2017).

A number of high survivability experiments have also been coordinated by this group, although not necessarily centred on the case study of DiscardLess.

Currently, the identification of choke species has also been a main task by this group. During March 2018 a prioritisation process, similar to the Choke Mitigation Tool used in the North Western Waters and North Sea, is being conducted with the Member States group, the SWWAC and AZTI scientists. As part of this process management options to avoid these choke effects are also under consideration. In fact, inter-species quota flexibility (IQF) has been considered as the main promising tool, once the use of other more traditional options, such as international swaps, have been exhausted. However, there are several perceived shortcomings with this IQF option, especially related to how and when this management option should be implemented. There has also been discussion of the use of bycatch quotas as a partial solution. Additionally the possibility of removing TACs from some stocks with Zero TACs has been discussed.

From the perspective of NGO's not enough has been done by managers to implement the LO, they feel that there is too much emphasis on exemptions and many of them are in favour of using Article 17 to give a greater allocation to fleets with lower discards.

6.5 Azores Case Study

The LO will only apply to Azorean bottom fisheries in 2019. In advance of this there has been a significant focus by managers on management measures and in particular on the possibility of high survival and possibly *de minimis* exemptions also. Blackspot Sea Bream and some species of deep-water sharks are being considered for a high survival exemption and DiscardLess scientists have been working closely on fishing trials to assess survival rates and handling practices for a number of species in order to improve survivability.

There have been some proposed LO related changes to quota management including the adoption of ITQs in order to accommodate fishers without quota for Blackspot Seabream.

The perception in the Azores is that the bottom fisheries, as they are line fisheries are already very selective, with low discard rates, and that further selectivity improvements will be very difficult to achieve. Additionally fishers feel that avoidance strategies would not be particularly successful either as there are a mix of sizes of fish in most areas. Accordingly fishers feel that the LO is not particularly relevant to the Azores. Environmental NGOs in the Azores are more concerned about overcapacity than the LO.

The choke species in the Azores would be alfonsinos (*Beryx* spp) and blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*). There is also still a big uncertainty around the deep-water sharks, that are TAC 0 species, and what will happen regarding them with the LO.

The table below, reproduced from the Year 2 case study report for the Azores, shows the main changes in management measures which have taken place since 2010.

Management measure	Species	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Quota	Deep-Water Sharks (DWS)	Implementation of the TAC 0; allowance of max 10% of 2009 quota (10t) as bycatch	0; allowance of max 3% of 2009 quota (10t) taken as bycatch	0	0	0	0	0	0; allowance of max 10t taken as bycatch	
	DWS species list	15 taxa*			<i>Galeus melastomus</i> removed; <i>Centrophorus</i> spp. added					
Quota	<i>Beryx</i> spp.	-	-	-	Implementation of the "80% notice"***	"80% notice"	"80% notice"	"80% notice"	"80% notice"	
Minimum landing size (MLS)	<i>Beryx splendens</i>	-	-	-	-	-	250 g	250 g	30 cm	
MLS	<i>Beryx decadactylus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	250 g	250 g	35 cm	
MLS	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	25 cm	25 cm	25 cm	25 cm	25 cm	30 cm	32 cm	33 cm	
Seasonal closure	<i>Pagellus bogaraveo</i>	-	-	-	-	-	15/01 to 29/02	15/01 to 29/02	15/01 to 31/01***	to

* List of deep-water sharks (DWS) for which 0 TAC has been applied since 2010: *Apristurus* spp., *Centroscymnus coelolepis*, *Centroscymnus crepidater*, *Chlamydoselachus anguineus*, *Centroscyllium fabricii*, *Dalatias licha*, *Deania calcea*, *Etmopterus princeps*, *Etmopterus spinax*, *Galeus melastomus*, *Galeus murinus*, *Hexanchus griseus*, *Oxynotus paradoxus*, *Scymnodon ringens*, *Somniosus microcephalus*.

** "80% notice" occurs when 80% of the shared *Beryx* spp. quota has been achieved and implies a 5% catch limit for *B. decadactylus* and a closure for *B. splendens*.

*** A new regulation 13/2017 approved by the Regional Government of the Azores revoked the seasonal closures for *Pagellus bogaraveo*.

6.6 North Sea and West of Scotland case study

UK

Managers in the UK strongly emphasise the benefits of more proactive use of Remote Electronic Monitoring (REM) in reducing discards and in implementing the LO. They are aware that this approach is not favoured by all MS. Managers have also stated that some version of the LO here to stay despite Brexit and that a public appetite for a discard ban is still evident. Previous trials with a Fully Documented Fishery (FDF) using cameras reduced discard rates but when the LO replaced the Cod Recovery Plan (CRP) incentivising of FDF by granting additional quota to vessels prepared to carry cameras became difficult.

Industry are concerned about the lack of a level playing field if widespread REM is introduced at national level but not throughout Europe (i.e. they would have to observe the LO while feeling others don't). Managers feel that their role could be in realigning compliance and enforcement resources away from traditional approaches and towards REM. The "level playing field" the industry are concerned about can be implemented across UK vessels and those fishing in UK waters. NGOs are also pushing for the use of cameras.

No major decrease in discard observer coverage has been noted to date although there are concerns regarding the potential use of MSS data in a control context. There is no appetite for the use of enhanced observer coverage as the advantages of REM are seen as much more significant.

Regarding the role of spatial management in discard mitigation UK authorities are familiar with the approach due to its use by Scotland for seven years as part of cod avoidance measures. Spatial approaches are well accepted by industry but there is some potential for abuse of the system, depending on how closures are triggered. Managers see their role in any use of spatial management measures in communicating the measures effectively and in ensuring robust evidence behind the decisions on closures.

Regarding avoidance measures UK managers recognise their popularity with the industry but see it as a very hands off approach and of limited benefit if everyone isn't on board and supportive.

Quota uplift has been the main tool used to implement the landing obligation but due to a lack of adequate enforcement status quo behaviours with regards to discarding have been evident with commensurate increases in fishing mortality. Choke species have been a convenient scapegoat. This

increase in F has been recognised by many in industry as being an unwelcome and unsustainable development.

The use of *de minimis* exemptions is strongly supported by the industry. However there is still some uncertainty in the scale of how they would be applied whether that would be at haul, trip or annual levels and at vessel, fleet or MS levels. The lack of data on survival remains a barrier to the use of high survival exemptions. Exemptions are seen as difficult to implement and they introduce loopholes in regulation.

Regarding the potential use of RTI's managers noted that this approach was an exploratory one being examined in an academic context, but was a long way from practical implementation in Scotland.

Denmark

In Denmark, important changes have occurred in 2017 regarding the management of fisheries. First, a suite of political decisions were taken by the Opposition parties outside of the Government, leading to a new set of management measures in the "Fiskeripakken" (<http://www.ft.dk/samling/20161/almdel/mof/bilag/158/1700413.pdf>). Then during summer 2017, significant media coverage focused on the so-called "scandal of the quota kings", where the Ministry of Environment and Food and corresponding AgriFish Agency were strongly criticized for insufficient control of the transferable quotas, leading to too much quotas ending up in too few hands. As a result, the entire responsibility of fisheries management was transferred to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, under the authority of a different minister. Finally, in late 2017 / early 2018, new media headlines exposed the sustained high discards in the Baltic in spite of the landing obligation (Baltic Sea 2020, 2017⁴). These important political changes have led to a lot of new staff and potentially a different approach to management. It has not been possible to proceed yet with interviews with the new managerial staff in the frame of DiscardLess; nevertheless, it is obvious that there is intense political focus on fisheries management issues at present, and several elements point towards a reconsideration of options for fully documented fisheries, as mentioned under Fiskeripakken points 6 and 7.

⁴ See also <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/penge/s-og-df-kraever-kontrol-af-fiskere-kun-boeder-ulovligt-udsmid-af-fisk>

7 Conclusions

One of the outstanding aspects evident when analysing management measures with regards to implementation of the Landing obligation is that there is significant inertia with regards to concrete measures taken. There are few examples of significant changes to quota regimes or new management approaches that can be highlighted and no magic bullet solution to the choke species problem has been identified. Management measures can at best be described as being incrementally changed and even the ones most relied on, the use of high survival and *de minimis* exemptions, are being sought and granted but not being used by fishers. There appears to a certain extent to be an impasse or stalemate with most member states waiting for some catalyst before more significant action will be taken. There may be a number of reasons for this including:

- the relatively short time scales within which it is reasonable to expect significant change. Governance changes tend to happen in an evolutionary rather than revolutionary manner.
- Some member states may not be as supportive of the need for a change in the approach to discard management as others or it appears at least that some are stronger advocates of the LO as a good vehicle with which to change discard practices.

In any case a striking diversity of views was evident during our interviews between MS regarding which management measures should be used and how. Some member states are keen on applying a control-based approach relying on REM and feel that the over reliance on exemptions introduces loopholes and preserves the status quo. Other member states are focussing almost solely on these exemptions and appear to be implementing the LO in a purely mechanical manner. Others are keen to foster a gradual change in mindset throughout the catching sector that discarding is wasteful and needs to be reduced. Such member states seek to positively incentivise more selective fishing through a combination of funding of selectivity projects and associated quota schemes which encourage the uptake of such gears. However such a long-term approach is not well aligned with the timescale for LO implementation, which requires that all TAC species are fully covered by 2019. Industry representatives argue that this mindset may be there already but that the legislative drivers and incentives have been misaligned and in the past were requiring fishers to discard.

A published summary of a DG Mare seminar on the LO held on November 15th 2017 in Brussels states that what is needed now is *“a more detailed assessment of the possible technical solutions and what the implications of these may be in terms of the impact on other target species and what other measures may be required if technical solutions were not available”*. This highlights that the outstanding task remains one of finding solutions and not identifying the problems. A recent STECF expert working group met with the task of quantifying the impact that improved selectivity measures would have on choke mitigation and the economic impacts also (STECF EWG 18 02). The analysis in this report shows that we

are to a certain extent seeing a very slow progression from identifying the problems to contemplating the solutions but with little real implementation of such solutions as yet.

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